

Organic Pesticides. Part VII. Synthesis of certain Fluoro-acridines

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3-Fluoro-5-chloro-7-bromoacridine, 3,7-difluoro-5-chloroacridine and its 5-substituted derivatives, the isomers 3-fluoro-4-nitro-5-chloroacridine and 2-nitro-3-fluoro-5-chloroacridine, and their 5-substituted derivatives have been synthesised as potential pest-control chemicals.

Usually, an unsubstituted nucleus containing heterocyclic nitrogen is seldom fungitoxic. Acridine is, however, known to be toxic to spores of various rusts (Straib, *Zentral. Bakt. Abs.* 2., 1941, 103, 73). Horsfall and Rich (Contributions from Boyce Thomson Institute, 1951, 16, 316) evaluated a large number of heterocyclic nitrogen compounds by the spore-germination technique against *Sclerotinia fructicola* and *Macrosporium sarcinaeforme* and found acridine to be fairly active. The only work done so far on fluoro-acridines is by Wilkinson and Finar (*J. Chem., Soc.*, 1947, 759). We have therefore attempted to synthesise acridines containing fluorine, either in the nucleus or in addition in an aromatic side chain at position 5.

4-Fluoro-3-nitroaniline was condensed with *o*-chlorobenzoic acid to obtain 4'-fluoro-3'-nitrodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid (I) having a substituent in position 3', which on cyclisation with phosphorus oxychloride gave two isomeric acridines depending on whether the ring closure occurred at 2'- or 6'-position. These were separated from toluene by fractional crystallisation (vide Experimental).

We have not been able to synthesise by an additional independent method either of these isomers so far and the structures assigned to them are based on observations made earlier by various workers in similar other cases (Lehmstedt and Schrader, *Ber.*, 1937, 70, 838; Albert and Linnell, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 377; Bradburry and Linnell, *ibid.*, 1942, 377). In all these cases a negative substituent in 3'-position is reported to provide a ratio of *ortho* to *para* closure as 75:25, whereas a positive substituent, about 20:80. Keeping in view these generalisations and our own observations, we have provisionally suggested the structures (II, yield 67%) and (III, yield 33%). The other fluoro-acridines were prepared by the usual method.

EXPERIMENTAL

4'-Fluoro-3'-nitrodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic Acid (I) was obtained by refluxing *o*-chlorobenzoic acid (45 g.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (45 g.), 4-fluoro-3-nitroaniline (56 g.), amyl alcohol (150 c.c.), and freshly prepared dry copper powder (3g.) at 140° for 5 hours. The resulting solution was steam distilled, diluted with water, boiled with animal charcoal, and filtered. The filtrate on acidification gave a solid which crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 175°, yield 45 g. (46%). (Found: N, 10.02%. $C_{13}H_9O_4N_2F$ requires N, 10.14%).

Formation of 3-Fluoro-4-nitro-5-chloroacridine (II) and *3-Fluoro-2-nitro-5-chloroacridine* (III).—The compound (I) (45 g.) and $POCl_3$ (150 c.c.) were heated on a steam bath for 15 minutes and then in an oil bath at 120° for 4 hours. Excess of $POCl_3$ was removed under reduced pressure at a bath temperature of 140° and the resulting liquid was poured into a well-stirred, cold solution of ammonia and chloroform. The chloroform layer was separated, washed with water, dried, chloroform evaporated, and the solid obtained was dried *in vacuo*; yield 30 g., m.p. 120°.

The product was gently refluxed with toluene for a few minutes and filtered hot. The undissolved residue was repeatedly extracted with boiling toluene, filtered, and finally washed with cold toluene. This insoluble product was assigned the structure (III), yield 10 g., m.p. 265° (decomp.). (Found: N, 9.92%. $C_{13}H_6O_2N_2ClF$ requires N, 10.12%). The residue obtained on evaporation of the mother liquor weighed 20 g., m. p. 155° (decomp.) and was assigned the structure (II). (Found: N, 9.96%. $C_{13}H_6O_2N_2ClF$ requires N, 10.12%).

Formation of 3-Fluoro-4-nitro-5-phenoxyacridine was effected by heating 3-fluoro-4-nitro-5-chloroacridine (2 g.) with phenol (10 g.) at 120° for 3 hours and then pouring the mixture into 2*N*-NaOH (60 c.c.). It was filtered, the yellow product obtained was washed with ether, and finally crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 135°, yield 1.7 g. (70.8%). (Found: N 8.26. $C_{19}H_{11}O_3N_2F$ requires N, 8.38%).

3-Fluoro-4-nitro-5-phenylaminoacridine—3-Fluoro-4-nitro-5-chloroacridine (3 g.), aniline (1.5 g.), and phenol (15 g.) were heated on a steam bath for 4 hours. The mixture was cooled, triturated with ether, and filtered. The residue was washed several times with ether, dried, and dissolved in acetic acid; the solution was decomposed with ammonia and filtered. A scarlet-red product was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 125°, yield 1 g. (27.7%). (Found: N, 12.54. $C_{19}H_{12}O_2N_3F$ requires N 12.61%).

3-Fluoro-2-nitro-5-phenoxyacridine was obtained from 3-fluoro-2-nitro-5-chloroacridine (2 g.) and phenol (10 g.) by following the above procedure. The product was dull yellow in colour, m.p. 245°, yield 2 g. (83.3%). (Found: N, 8.22. $C_{19}H_{11}O_3N_2F$ requires N, 8.38%).

3-Fluoro-2-nitro-5-phenylaminacridine was prepared from 3-fluoro-2-nitro-5-chloroacridine (3 g.), aniline (1.5 g.), and phenol (15 g.) by following the above procedure. A dull red product was obtained; m.p. 250°, yield 1.2 g. (33.2%). (Found: N, 12.48. $C_{19}H_{12}O_2N_3F$ requires N, 12.61%).

4,4'-Difluorodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid (IV) was obtained by refluxing a mixture of 3-fluoro-6-bromobenzoic acid (21 g.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (14 g.), *p*-fluoroaniline (16 g.), amyl-alcohol (60 c.c.), and a trace of freshly prepared dry copper powder according to the procedure given earlier. The compound is light grey in colour, m.p. 220° (decomp.), yield 16.5 g. (69.3%). (Found: N, 5.51. $C_{13}H_9O_2NF_2$ requires N, 5.62%).

Formation of 3,7-Difluoro-5-chloroacridine.—The compound (IV) (16.5 g.) was cyclised by means of $POCl_3$ (55 c.c.) according to the procedure mentioned earlier, yielding 3,7-difluoro-5-chloroacridine. The product is yellowish green in colour, m.p. 169°, yield 15 g. (90%). (Found: N, 5.51. $C_{13}H_6NClF_2$ requires N, 5.61%).

3,7-Difluoro-5-phenoxyacridine was obtained from the above compound (2 g.) and phenol (10 g.) by the usual procedure and crystallised from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 161° (decomp.), yield 2.0 g. (83.3%). (Found: N, 4.42. $C_{19}H_{11}ONF_2$ requires N, 4.56%).

3,7-Difluoro-5-phenylaminoacridine.—The above compound (5 g.), aniline (2 g.), and phenol (30 g.) were heated on a steam bath for 4 hours. The mixture was triturated with ether when the hydrochloride separated. It was filtered and washed well with ether, m.p. 335°, yield 5 g. (73.5%). (Found: N, 8.07. $C_{19}H_{13}N_2ClF_2$ requires N, 8.17%).

The hydrochloride was dissolved in acetic acid and the free base was liberated by decomposing the acetic acid solution in cold with ammonia, m.p. 193°, yield 3.5 g. (57.3%). (Found: N, 9.02. $C_{19}H_{12}N_2F_2$ requires N, 9.14%).

3,7-Difluoro-5-*p*-fluorophenylaminoacridine was obtained from the previous compound (2.5 g.), *p*-fluoroaniline (1.5 g.), and phenol (15 g.) by the above procedure. Yield of the hydrochloride was 3 g. (83.3%), m.p. 350°. (Found: N, 7.64. $C_{19}H_{12}N_2ClF_3$ requires N, 7.73%). Yield of the free base was 2 g. (62.5%), m.p. 198°. (Found: N, 8.48. $C_{19}H_{11}N_2F_3$ requires N, 8.64%).

3,7-Difluoro-5- α -naphthylaminoacridine was obtained from the previous compound (3 g.), α -naphthylamine (3 g.), and phenol (20 g.) by following the above procedure. Yield of the hydrochloride was 3 g. (50.8%), m.p. 172°. (Found: N, 6.89. $C_{23}H_{15}N_2ClF_2$ requires N, 7.13%). Yield of the free base was 2 g. (46.7%) m.p. 73°. (Found: N, 7.64. $C_{23}H_{14}N_2F_2$ requires N, 7.86%).

4'-Fluoro-4-bromodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid was obtained by refluxing 2-chloro-5-bromobenzoic acid (prepared by the method of Cohen and Smithells, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 1911) (1.5 g.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (2 g.), *p*-fluoroaniline (2 g.),

amyl alcohol (5 c.c.), and a trace of freshly prepared dry copper powder; m.p. 190° (decomp.), yield 1.5 g. (76%). (Found: N 4.32. $C_{13}H_9O_2NBrF$ requires N, 4.50%).

Formation of 3-Fluoro-7-bromo-5-chloroacridine.—The above compound (1.5 g.) and $POCl_3$ (5 c.c.) by the usual procedure afforded 3-fluoro-7-bromo-5-chloroacridine, m.p. 135°, yield 1 g. (66%). (Found : N, 4.38. $C_{13}H_6NBrClF$ requires N, 4.50%).

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